

THE IDEA OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN INTERSTATE RELATIONS

E.S.Sultonova, R.A.Abdullaeva

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Uzbekistan.

The concept of international collaboration holds a pivotal role in global dynamics. Following its independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan promptly initiated diplomatic and cooperative engagements with various prominent and advanced nations globally. More recently, an open and pragmatic approach to foreign policy has notably reinforced Uzbekistan's relationships with its neighboring states. A noteworthy development in this realm is the burgeoning collaboration with the Republic of Azerbaijan, a key geostrategic nation in the South Caucasus, underscoring the significance of international cooperation in the matrix of interstate relationships. A scholarly examination of interstate relations and international cooperation is crucial for a deeper understanding of these dynamics.

The theoretical framework concerning interstate cooperation has emerged as a critical area of study, particularly given its escalating relevance in contemporary international relations. The exploration of the nuances of interstate cooperation became a distinct academic pursuit in the latter half of the 20th century. This academic interest was largely propelled by the substantial escalation in the volume and complexity of interstate interactions over the past five decades. Moreover, the evolving geopolitical landscape increasingly compels state actors to adopt cooperative strategies as mechanisms to address contemporary global conflicts, thereby considering the interests of a broad spectrum of stakeholders. The proliferation of integration processes and cooperative domains has significantly shaped the development of international relations and institutions, placing the dynamics of interstate cooperation at the forefront of discussions within classical theoretical frameworks.

Regardless of the differences in the political, economic and social structure of the states, the idea of international cooperation is inseparable from the goal of maintaining international peace and security and is the main rule in the system of norms of the UN Charter.[9]

The works of J.P. Derriennic, and R. Keohane are of great importance among the scientists who research the issue of cooperation. Also, V. Levashova, A. Wolfers,

and A. Wendt touched on the issue of cooperation throughout their scientific research. Although their views differ, there is one idea that unites all scientists and that is the idea that there is cooperation. As a result of the rapid changes in the current chaotic world, the appearance of interstate cooperation is expanding, developing and becoming more modern.

J.P. Derriennic defining the issue of cooperation, emphasizes that two actors cooperate - when one party is satisfied, the other party is also satisfied. He pointed out that the outcome of a purely cooperative relationship can be a situation that satisfies both actors or none of them.[1] Based on this, the cooperating countries should benefit, even if they are not the same. Cooperation can be with one or more countries. Also, there is activity based on one common goal in international cooperation. We can be sure of this when analyzing the views of Keohane Robert and A.V. Levashova. According to their concepts, it is possible to distinguish several aspects of interstate cooperation: first, interstate cooperation is considered a process of coordination and implementation of decisions aimed at mutual benefit; secondly, they prove that the actions of any actor are aimed at achieving certain goals. Thus, in the process of studying the theory of international cooperation, scientists tried to prove its emergence and its ability to serve to ensure stability.

If we analyze the approaches of representatives of classical theories of international relations to the issue of international cooperation, it should be noted that representatives of the theory of political realism are skeptical about the existence of cooperation. This is a very difficult issue for them. Realists, whose main emphasis is on security, power and war, believe that cooperation is impossible. But some of them, including A. Wolfers recognized that the main meaning of cooperation is defined as "a necessary condition for the successful implementation of the policy of balance of power"[5]. According to him, there are two types of interstate cooperation: "internally oriented" and "externally oriented" cooperation. "Internal-oriented" cooperation is aimed at improving the internal relations of the states and is carried out independently without external threats. "Externally oriented" cooperation is a cooperation directed to overcome a common external threat, and in this way, states unite or form an alliance.

Another scientist, Kenneth Oye, in his realist views, focused on the issue of cooperation in anarchy. Although an important part of the researcher's program is focused on anarchy, it also provides aspects of the implementation of cooperation, and it is mentioned that states have the opportunity to implement cooperation to achieve common interests in the conditions of anarchy.

Based on the above analysis, we conclude that the characteristics of a realistic approach to the issue of international cooperation are as follows:

- *international cooperation, as a rule, is reduced to interstate relations based on mutual recognition of sovereignty and non-interference of cooperating parties in each other's affairs;*
- *the most important incentive for states to cooperate is the anarchism of the international environment: cooperation is organized where there is a conflict or threat;*
- *the main goal of interstate cooperation is security, and its original, simplest and most common form is a military (military-political) alliance.*

Another classic theory of international relations, political liberalism, developed widely after the end of the First World War. There is a wide range of different strands of the theory of political Liberalism in international relations. But it is Mark Zacher and Richard Matthews who have discussed well what all liberal approaches have in common. They identify three general theories. First, liberals assume that international relations are aimed at gradually increasing human freedom by establishing conditions of peace, prosperity, and justice. In contrast to neorealists' visions of an anarchic international system characterized by perpetual war, liberals see development as at least a distinct possibility, not inevitable. "The second thesis is that the central point in the realization of human freedom is the development of international cooperation." [6] The third general thesis of the approaches of the theory of political liberalism is that the change in international relations is connected with the modernization processes based on the scientific and intellectual revolution of liberalism. Based on these theses, Zacher and Matthew make conclusions about the fact that individuals are important international actors, that national interests can change, and that they are formed as a result of internal and external influences. In this context, the importance of focusing on both domestic politics and external international events is implied in the analysis of international relations. Finally, theories of political liberalism assume that international regimes and cooperation based on mutual interests are possible, and believe that states can unite in pursuit of mutual interests, that is, they are mutually agreeable. This is an important vision for sustainability and a better future. It should also not be forgotten that cooperation and conflict are two processes inherent like international relations, and the complete exclusion of one of them can lead to the gradual exclusion of the other.

In modern conditions, the study of interstate cooperation processes is of particular importance, because they are the only non-violent way to resolve international conflicts.

Representatives of the theory of constructivism, who want to act as a bridge between the theories of realism and liberalism, are scientists such as Alexander Wendt, Nicholas Onuf, Friedrich Kratochwill, Emanuel Adler, among whom Wendt's theory has a key place. According to the views of constructivists, the action of the state in the international arena is variable depending on its interests and identity. The behavior of states in the system of international relations and conducting international foreign relations is in the process of transformation. Also, the main basis of Constructivism is international relations, regions, international organizations, states, people, nation, society and other concepts - the product of human consciousness and thinking. Concepts are formed using a certain set of ideas, that is, a construction. The formation of ideas is influenced by the identity of the society. [7, 13p] Identity is not immutable, it can change over time under the influence of certain situations or circumstances. It develops over time, just like the interests of the state. From this perspective, constructivists emphasize that the interests of states, interstate relations, and issues of international cooperation change over time. International cooperation between countries with similar characteristics develops in a relatively stable and moderate manner.

In summarizing, it is pertinent to acknowledge that the theme of cooperation represents a subject extensively explored within academic circles, yet it continues to attract significant scholarly interest. In the analysis of interstate relationships, it is crucial to comprehensively assess all facets of the relations between the states under study, evaluating the development and prospective sustainability of their cooperation, as well as the measures both parties undertake to sustain such relationships. Specifically, in the context of Uzbekistan-Azerbaijan bilateral cooperation, the congruence and divergence in perspectives between the two countries play a critical role in shaping the dynamics of international cooperation.

Furthermore, propelled by its open and pragmatic foreign policy, Uzbekistan has notably accelerated the expansion of its international relations and cooperative endeavors in recent years. This proactive approach has facilitated the establishment of new areas of cooperation with Azerbaijan, alongside a general intensification of its international collaborative efforts. This evolution underscores the dynamic nature of international cooperation and highlights the ongoing importance of adaptive and forward-thinking foreign policy strategies in today's geopolitical landscape.

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